

Research

Examining the Role of Oral Fluid HCV Self-Testing in Enhancing Hepatitis C Screening Acceptance Rates: A Systematic Review

Mon Yee Htet Paing^{1*}, Ye Win Naing¹, Khin Yadana Aung¹

¹Health Science Centre, Xi'an Jiao Tong University, Xi'An, Shaanxi, China. 710061

Abstract: Self-testing for hepatitis C is a promising approach to increasing testing, particularly in high-risk areas. To eliminate HCV as a public health issue by 2030, it is critical to make it easier for those most affected to receive testing, treatment, and healthcare. The study aims to assess the Examining the Role of Oral Fluid HCV Self-Testing in Enhancing Hepatitis C Screening Acceptance Rates among the public and health professionals for diagnosing and treating HCV, with the aim of making new tests more useful and accessible. The acceptability of oral fluid HCV self-testing for Hepatitis C diagnosis is crucial for several reasons. It can provide a discreet, convenient alternative for high-risk populations. Oral fluid self-testing can be performed at home, reducing barriers related to clinic visits, and providing privacy and confidentiality. It can also help design interventions for early diagnosis and linkage to care. Increasing HCV testing rates through acceptable methods can have a significant impact on public health, leading to earlier diagnosis and improved treatment outcomes. Its cost-effectiveness makes it a worthwhile investment in resource-limited settings. A systematic review on the efficacy of hepatitis C virus self-testing was conducted with study duration of December 2023-May 2024 using databases like Science Direct, Cochrane, PubMed, and Medline. PRISMA's methodologies and reporting guidelines guided the search. The included study range was 10 years window from 2014-2024 initial search yielded 210 publications, but the number of articles that required examination was reduced after applying selected keywords and evaluating abstracts. We deemed 25 articles relevant to the subject after applying inclusion and exclusion criteria. The findings are analyzed, highlighting their limitations and strengths and discussing practical implications, knowledge gaps, and recommendations for future research. This study provides evidence supporting the feasibility and widespread acceptance of oral fluid HCV self-testing, a method that has the potential to overcome barriers to facility-based HCV testing.

Keywords: Hepatitis C virus, HCV Self-Testing, Acceptability, Rapid diagnostic tests, Usability

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 12 June, 2024; **Published:** 25 June, 2024

How to cite this article: Mon Yee Htet Paing, Ye Win Naing, Khin Yadana Aung (2024). Examining the Role of Oral Fluid HCV Self-Testing in Enhancing Hepatitis C Screening Acceptance Rates: A Systematic Review. *North American Academic Research*, 7(6), 69-92. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12684643>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

The Hepatitis C virus (HCV) is a significant global contributor to viral hepatitis, cirrhosis, and liver cancer, affecting 71 million people and resulting in 400,000 deaths each year[1]. Eighty percent of the infected people reside in low- and middle-income nations, where the virus is more prevalent [2]. The WHO estimates that less than 25% of HCV infections receive a diagnosis, with around 40% of cases going untreated. Genotype 1 affects an estimated three to four million people annually, with genotypes 2 and 3 following suit. Genotypes 4, 5, and 6 exhibit distinct geographical trends [3]. In countries where HCV infections are common, dangerous needle drug use and dirty medical treatments are two of

the main things that put people at risk of getting them. Diagnostic approaches include testing for blood antibodies, measuring RNA, determining viral genotype and subtype, and assessing resistance-associated substitution [4]. The World Health Organisation (WHO) has set national goals to eradicate hepatitis C by 2030, focusing on political support, fundraising, and multisectoral cooperation. This strategy, alongside potent antivirals, has sparked global efforts to increase screening and treatment capacity [5]. Direct-acting antiviral treatment (DAA) has revolutionized the world's response to the hepatitis C virus (HCV). This pan-genotypic, short-course treatment prevents the virus from multiplying and allows it to function. Despite 9.4 million people taking DAA, low uptake and shame concerns limit treatment growth. Combining DAAs can cure over 90% of HCV patients, even in difficult-to-treat communities. This combination results in long-lasting resistance against viruses twelve weeks after treatment. [4,6,7]. Self-testing for HIV, as suggested by the World Health Organisation since 2016, involves individuals taking their own samples for fast tests and understanding the results. This method is safe for high-risk groups and could help eradicate the virus. However, concerns arise about user mistakes and connecting positive results to confirmed testing, which could lead to confusion and potential misuse [8-10]. The studies suggests that genetic makeup and plasma virus load can effectively predict the effectiveness of a treatment. [11]. Rapid diagnostic tests (RDT) are used for hepatitis C virus (HCV) screening to identify antibodies in blood samples. Many affected individuals, particularly those with dangerous blood transfers or unclean medical tools, are unaware of their illness. Some groups, such as those who use drugs, have same-sex relationships, live with HIV, work as sex workers, or are mobile and foreign, face difficulties in accessing protection, evaluation, and treatment programmes due to their unique challenges[12]. To eradicate HCV as a public health issue by 2030, it is crucial to simplify testing, treatment, and health care for those most affected. Existing tests are insufficient, leading to the development of HCV self-testing. This study aims to determine the acceptance and feasibility of HCV self-testing among the general public, and health practitioners to determine its potential for treating HCV. The goal is to fill gaps in existing tests and improve access to HCV treatment.

Methodology

This systematic review investigates the acceptability of oral fluid HCV self-testing among different population groups and compares it with traditional blood-based testing to understand user preferences and satisfaction. The study assesses the linkage to care of individuals using oral fluid self-tests compared to those using traditional testing methods. A detailed search strategy was employed, using appropriate keywords and database-specific key/indexing terms related to Self-testing for Hepatitis C ", "Acceptability for HCV self-testing ", and "Hepatitis C virus." PICO criteria were used to formulate research questions, specifying population problem, intervention, comparison (if any), and outcomes that were evaluated and considered in analysis and synthesis of evidence. The study focuses on individuals aged 18 and older, high-risk populations for HCV, and general population samples for comparison. It is conducted in various geographic regions, including urban and rural settings, to ensure diverse representation. The inclusion criteria include efficacy studies, randomized clinical trials, cross-sectional studies, and meta-analysis. Exclusion criteria include studies reporting irrelevant outcomes, systematic or narrative reviews, letters, editorials, scientific reports, and longitudinal analysis-based studies, published before 2014, and studies in other languages than English. A well-structured data extraction form was established for the collection of appropriate information from the included studies, focusing on the Acceptability of Oral Fluid HCV Self-Testing for Hepatitis C Diagnosis. Boolean operations such as "OR" and "AND" were used to develop different search combinations. The Cochrane Risk of Bias tool (ROB) is used to assess the likelihood of bias in randomized controlled trials (RCTs). The Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) is a quality assessment tool that uses a star system to score observational studies on a scale of 0-9. A score between 7 and 9 indicates good quality, 4 to 6 indicates high risk, and 0 indicates very high risk of bias. The synthesis of the extracted data was done narratively, and results regarding the Acceptability of Oral Fluid HCV Self-Testing for Hepatitis C Diagnosis were organized systematically. Subgroup analyses and sensitivity analyses were performed where applicable. The results

were interpreted based on the strengths and restrictions of the studies included in the systematic review, explaining practical implications and research gaps in the knowledge, and suggesting potential suggestions for future research.

Figure 1: Flow Chart of Data Inclusion Strategy for Systematic Review

Result

The search yielded 38 publications, with 30 from the Cochrane Library, 75 from PubMed, 42 from Medline, and 63 from Science direct. Twelve were excluded due to insufficient emphasis on primary determinants, irrelevant results, challenges with clinical trial registries, unretrieved reports, and inaccessible full text records. The remaining 26 papers were selected for the study, assessing their quality through a thorough examination of the abstract, title, study type, and complete text availability.

Table: 1 Included studies

SL	Author/Year	Study Design	Outcome	Finding
1	[13]	Review based study	Acceptability and usability	The study reveals that oral fluid HCV self-testing is feasible and widely

				accepted for HCV testing, but requires assistance for correct sample collection and performance.
2	[14]	Observational Study	Usability and acceptability	The study found that oral fluid HCV self-testing is highly usable and acceptable in a general population, with 72% completing testing steps without assistance and interpreting results correctly, with 96% recommending it.
3	[15]	Observational Study	Usability and acceptability	The study found that participants were able to interpret results correctly, with some difficulty interpreting weak positive results.
4	[16]	cross-sectional study	Usability and acceptability	The research indicated that oral fluid HCV self-testing was received by PWID, with just a few reported side effects, including mistakes and withdrawal. There has to be more communication and education for this demographic, as well as direct help choices, because the majority of participants got the findings and understood them properly.
5	[17]	Observational Study	Usability and acceptability	The research concluded that Chinese had a good level of usage and acceptance for oral fluid HCV self-testing. The vast majority thought it was simple, would use it again, and even suggested it to others.
6	[18]	Observational Study	usability, acceptability and feasibility	Among Chinese MSM participants, oral fluid HCV self-testing was well received and easy to use; 54% of participants got all of the self-testing stages right and understood the findings.
7	[19]	observational study	Acceptability and Usability	The study found HCV self-testing acceptable among PWID and MSM in Thai Nguyen, with moderate to high usability, but lower concordance with study staff among older PWID.

8	[10]	Comparative Study	Clinical evaluation	<p>Self-testing oral fluid samples with the HCV Rapid Antibody Test worked well, with sensitivity, specificity, and κ statistic values of 88.4%, 100%, 97.7%, and 98% when skilled staff evaluated results.</p> <p>With HCV self-testing, the cost of diagnosing an HCV infection went up, but the cost of making a new diagnosis went down. In areas with a high incidence, introducing HCV self-testing is a more cost-effective option.</p>
9	[20]	Comparative Study	Cost-effectiveness	<p>Human Carcinoma Virus Rapid Antibody Test (HCV self-testing) usefulness and acceptability were evaluated in five countries in the research. With the majority of participants successfully completing the assessment, the results demonstrated a high level of use and acceptance in Georgia and Egypt. But for other groups, like PWID, supported self-testing models are essential. It is possible that HCV self-testing will be an effective method for drug removal.</p>
10	[21]	Comparative Study	usability and acceptability	<p>The study found that HCV self-testing is a creative way to get tested in Rwanda that makes testing easier for more people and lets people choose if they need more care.</p>
11	[22]	qualitative study	Values and preferences	<p>A study found that hepatitis C self-testing (HCV self-testing) is a creative way to make testing easier for more people.</p>
12	[23]	qualitative study	values and preferences	<p>The study found that self-testing could be more successful if it was offered for free in shops or harm reduction groups, with clear directions and information on how accurate the test was.</p>
13	[24]	qualitative study	Values and preferences	<p>Prototype HCV self-testing kits show high usability and interpretation.</p>
14	[25]	Observational Study	Usability	

15	[26]	RCT	self-testing	<p>The HCV self-testing made it possible for a lot more guys in China, both HIV-negative and HIV-positive, to get checked for HCV, and it cost less per person than normal care.</p> <p>HCV self-testing raised the number of tests and positive results compared to regular testing. It holds value for diverse populations and stakeholders, offering private, confidential results, autonomous decision-making, and increased education. HCV self-testing is high usability, cost-effective, and equitable, reaching more people and potentially increasing equity in diverse settings.</p>
16	[27]	Observational Study	self-testing	<p>Due to shame, discrimination, and privacy concerns, high-risk groups in areas with few resources don't get HIV tests as often as they should. HIV self-testing could make it easier for people to get tested and more often, but there are still problems with how it is being used. The study revealed that HIV testing prior to use and distribution of kits positively influenced their acceptance, while perceived risk negatively affected their acceptance.</p>
17	[28]	Observational Study	self-testing	<p>People who are a risk for HIV can do an HIV self-testing, and 77% of those at high risk said it was very acceptable. Most people tested because they wanted to, because it was free, or because they wanted quick answers. Most testing is done on-site, but 83% use kits every six months, and 71.7 % would rather test at home. The study found that having been tested for HIV before made people more likely to use and give out kits, while thinking they might get HIV made people less likely to give out kits.</p>
18	[29]	Longitudinal Study	Acceptability	
19	[30]	Longitudinal Study	Acceptability	

20	[31]	Exploratory study	Acceptability	This research examines the acceptability, consent, and uptake of free at-home HIV testing among those who engage in drug use. The findings indicate that 63.6% of participants express a likelihood of undergoing the test.
21	[32]	Observational Study	self-testing	This systematic study looks at how men get HIV care after getting a response HIV self-testing. Some barriers are not having enough money, social shame, discrimination, and worries about privacy.
22	[33]	Observational Study	self-testing	The first HIV-1/2 Antibody Self-Test developed by INSTI in Canada is capable of identifying HIV-1 and HIV-2 antibodies in blood samples. It exhibits a detection rate ranging from 50% to 99% for cases, however with a greater incidence of invalid test outcomes.
23	[34]	survey	Acceptability and usability	According to research, the poor adoption of HIV self-testing in Italy might be attributed to factors such as cost and privacy concerns. The report proposes several measures to enhance awareness, accessibility, and the quality of testing instructions.
24	[35]	Observational Study	self-testing	The efficacy of an uncontrolled HIV self-testing strategy in Metro Manila, Philippines was evaluated in this research, which reported a prevalence rate of 9.8% and a success rate of 95%.
25	[36]	survey	Acceptability	The efficacy of an HIV testing app (EPIC-HIV1) on tablets was investigated in a South African research including males between the ages of 15 and 24. The app was deemed acceptable and user-friendly by 96% of the participants, inspiring 83% to participate in the testing. But local clinics still faced obstacles.
26	[37]	Observational Study	self-testing	The rapid HCV test kit demonstrated excellent performance in self-testing oral

27	[38]	RCT	fluid specimens, with high agreement between patients and trained personnel on the interpretation of test results.
28	[39]	Observational Study	The study demonstrates positive experiences with oral fluid HCV self-tests in PWID and MSM populations, suggesting potential for other populations to learn their HCV status. Globally, HCV testing and treatment access is low, necessitating massive scale-up, innovative care models, political support, and investment for HCV elimination by 2030.
29	[40]	Observational Study	Low awareness of HCV among PWID in Kyrgyzstan could be increased through HCV self-testing, facilitated by peer-driven associations and addressing discrimination in healthcare institutions.
30	[41]	Observational Study	The global community must invest in patient-centric HCV diagnostic strategies and partnerships to ensure global elimination and increase access to curative treatment for millions in need.
31	[42]	Observational Study	The review highlights the lack of continent-wide standards and regulatory authority for IVD products in SSA, highlighting the industry's over-reliance on clinical performance and the lack of research on POC HCV IVDs.
32	[43]	RCT	OraQuick's rapid oral swab test matches EIA results, providing accurate diagnoses, but challenges need to be overcome for increased testing capacity and client access.
33	[44]	RCT	The study shows high usability and acceptability of oral fluid HCVST among Chinese MSM, but further research is needed to position and scale up HCVST effectively.
34	[45]	RCT	The UK is increasing HCV testing in prisons and Young Offender Institutions, with an oral antibody test. A project offered POCT to 107 male young

35	[46]	RCT	<p>offenders, monitoring HCV positivity and evaluating acceptability. Salivary rapid testing is acceptable but less sensitive.</p>
36	[47]	Observational Study	<p>The cost per HCV diagnosis varies by setting, with HCVST increasing the number of people tested, diagnosed, and cured but at higher costs. Self-testing increases the cost, while increased costs, substitution, low linkage, and low ST sensitivity increase the cost.</p> <p>The survey revealed that LMICs face significant barriers to increasing HBV and HCV diagnosis and treatment, including inadequate testing programs, lack of funding, public education, and skilled health professionals.</p>
37	[48]	Observational Study	<p>The World Health Organization (WHO) uses evidence appraisal in developing global health normative guidelines, ensuring they are informed by the latest evidence, feasibility, and considerations like user preferences, resource use, and human rights.</p>
38	[49]	RCT	<p>People with injection drug preferences show specific needs for HCV services, suggesting community-based risk reduction centers could be crucial for enhancing uptake and retention among this population.</p>
39	[50]	Observational Study	<p>The article discusses the importance of hepatitis C diagnostic packages in reducing public health care burden, addressing affordability, accessibility, and health system barriers, and implementing policy measures.</p>
40	[51]	Observational Study	<p>This article explores technological innovations for affordable and simplified HIV/HCV infection testing and treatment response monitoring, including alternative sampling methods, molecular assays, and health system improvements.</p>

A summary of the studies is presented in the Table 1:

According to Perazzo et al. (2023), oral fluid HCV self-testing was possible and well-liked, so it should be thought about for HCV tests in key groups of people. In 2021, a study in Egypt by Reipold et al. examined the willingness of individuals to self-test for hepatitis C virus antibodies, finding that 72.2% of those who took the test successfully completed it. Chan et al.'s 2024 study revealed that both general public and males who engage in sexual intercourse strongly prefer self-tests for hepatitis C based on oral fluid or blood, suggesting the need for inclusion in existing testing offerings. Ivanova Reipold et al. (2022) found high acceptability of HCV self-testing among drug users, suggesting increased messaging and education, including direct assistance options, could enhance acceptance

Fajardo et al.'s 2022 study in Guangzhou, China, found that oral fluid HCV self-testing is highly usable and acceptable among marginalized key populations, with most rating it as easy. Xu et al.'s 2022 study evaluated HCV Rapid Antibody Test's usability and acceptability among MSMs, finding high accuracy rates. Further research is recommended for improved system effectiveness. The study by Nguyen et al. (2021) evaluated the acceptability and usability of the OraQuick® HCV Self-Test among drug users and men in Thai Nguyen, finding high acceptability but lower concordance with study staff.

Kimble et al.'s 2019 study found 88.4% sensitivity and 100% specificity in oral fluid specimen self-testing when patients interpreted, and 97.7% and 98% when trained staff interpreted. Walker et al. (2023) found that HCV self-testing increased HCV diagnosis and cure rates but was more costly, especially in high-prevalence populations. A new approach to increasing the adoption of HCV self-testing has been identified by Serumondo et al. (2021), however there are some drawbacks to consider, such as the absence of counseling and the possibility of mental injury. Hepatitis C self-testing, according to a study from 2021, is a new way to make testing easier for more people, but it also brings up worries about mistakes and mental health issues.. Martínez-Pérez et al. (2021) highlighted the public health issue of low hepatitis C awareness among drug users, suggesting rapid self-testing kits could improve treatment acceptance, especially when delivered in pharmacies. A study by Majam et al. (2021) found that three prototype HCV self-testing kits are user-friendly, fast, private, and convenient, but there's confusion about IFU steps and finger-pricking

When compared to conventional care, Wang et al. (2023) discovered that self-testing for HIV considerably raised the percentage of males who tested for HCV and was less expensive overall. Ferner et al. (2021) discovered that HCV self-testing improves testing uptake, positivity, privacy, decision-making, education, usability, cost-effectiveness, and equity. Balakrishnan et al. (2023) highlight the underutilization of HIV testing in high-risk populations in resource-limited areas, despite the potential for improved self-testing. A study by Pincus et al. (2024) suggests that HIV self-testing could boost HIV testing access among PWID, with prior testing positively influencing kit usage and distribution. A study in Louisville, Kentucky, found that 77% of high-risk individuals accept HIV self-testing, with reasons including desire, freedom, and short results. Onsite testing is preferred by 83% and 71.7%). The study by Ballard et al. (2021) explores the acceptability, consent, and uptake of free at-home HIV testing among drug users in Rural Central Appalachia, US, finding that 63.6% participants are likely to take the tests. The systematic review by Hlongwa et al. (2023) examines men's linkage to HIV care post-reactive HIVST in, highlighting barriers like financial constraints, stigma, discrimination, and privacy concerns. Mason & Bailey (2023) found that self-testing, a method to reduce HIV infection, has gained popularity in Canada. The INSTI HIV-1/2 Antibody Self-Test, the first in Canada, detects HIV-1 and HIV-2 antibodies from blood. Nash et al.'s 2021 study revealed low HIV self-test uptake in Lithuania due to cost and incorrect results, while Italy faces privacy and confidentiality concerns. Strategies include increased awareness, targeted campaigns, and improved testing instructions. The study by Rosadiño et al. (2023) assessed the effectiveness of an unassisted HIV self-testing model in Metro Manila, Philippines, revealing a 9.8% prevalence and a 95% success rate. Dlamini et al.'s 2020 study found that 96% of men aged 15-24 found the EPIC-HIV1 tablet-based application acceptable and user-friendly, motivating 83% to test, despite lingering barriers to local clinics.

Table: 2 Excluded studies

SL	Author/year	title	Reason of Exclusion
1	[52]	This research protocol outlines a quasi-randomized controlled experiment that aims to provide hepatitis C self-testing for important demographics in Malaysia using internet platforms.	Clinical trial registry
2	[53]	This study aims to compare the self-reported levels of hepatitis B,C, and HIV status with the data obtained from oral fluid assays among convicts in Ireland.	Irrelevant outcome
3	[54]	Advancements in testing technology and methodologies for viral hepatitis testing: shaping the future	Irrelevant outcome
5	[55]	Researchers in sub-Saharan Africa tested the feasibility of a whole-blood multiplex immunochromatographic rapid test for HIV, HBV, and HCV using finger sticks.	Not focus on primary determinant
6	[56]	Advice and suggestions on how to test for the Hepatitis C virus on your own :	Reports not retrieved
7	[57]	Household Sample A Review of Lab Implementation Issues in Response to the Increased Demand for Screening for Sexually Transmitted Infections Due to the COVID-19 Pandemic	Irrelevant outcome
8	[58]	A strategy for a randomized waitlist-controlled study in China aims to minimize risk compensation among males who engage in sexual activity with men who take oral pre-exposure prophylaxis by promoting self-testing for HIV and other sexually transmitted infections (STIs).	Clinical trial registry
9	[59]	Prompt Urgent Call to Action to Increase HCV Self-Testing in the USA	Full text not available
10	[60]	This study aims to investigate the impact of HIV self-testing availability on the frequency of HIV testing among males who engage in sexual activity with other men. The study follows a stepped-wedge randomized controlled trial procedure.	Clinical trial registry
11	[61]	A comparative analysis of home-based versus clinic-based testing for HIV, syphilis, and	Full text not available

12	[62]	<p>hepatitis B in the cities of Birmingham and Solihull.</p> <p>This qualitative study aims to explore the barriers faced by males who involve in sexual activity with other men and transgender women in Bangladesh while accessing HIV testing services.</p>	Full text not available
----	------	--	-------------------------

A summary of the studies is presented in the Table 2:

A study compares normal care with an online HCV self-testing tool in Malaysia to see how well it works and how acceptable it is. The study's sample size goal is 750 people, and it will look at testing uptake, connection to care, acceptance, and possible social problems. There were differences between what prisoners from nine Irish jails said about their hepatitis B, C, and HIV infection status and what the oral fluid test results showed. Self-reported rates of hepatitis infection were lower than oral fluid test rates, but rates of HIV infection were about the same. The study found that self-reported results are not accurate and should not be used to plan services to help prisoners stay healthy and get better. Every prisoner should be able to get checked for these bugs. There are still cases of hepatitis that haven't been identified, and 257 million people around the world have chronic B and HCV illnesses. Better quick recognition technology can make it easier for people to get care, keep track of their treatments, and get to them. It can also help health systems work together better and combine data more securely. A cross-sectional study looked at how useful and acceptable a prototype finger-stick whole blood Triplex HIV/HCV self-test was for checking for HIV, HBV, and HCV all at the same time. 242 (96.4%) of the people who took the test were able to pass it, giving it a total usefulness score of 89.2%. The study shows that the Triplex self-test could be used on a big scale in groups of people who are at high risk for getting HIV, HBV, and HCV illnesses. The COVID-19 outbreak has sped up the development of syphilis, gonorrhea, and chlamydia self-testing and data gathering kits that can be used at home. Telemedicine companies let people pick up their own specimens, which could have perks like more tests, more privacy, and ease of use.

Risk of Bias 2 (ROB 2)-

It's essential to evaluate the quality and potential biases of the included studies to assess the reliability of the evidence.

Table 3: Quality Assessment for RCT

<p>Quality Assessment for RCT</p>
--

	Random Sequence Generation (Selection Bias)	Allocation Concealment (Selection Bias)	Binding Of Participation And Personnel (Performance Bias)	Binding Of Outcome Assessment (Detection Bias)	Incomplete Outcome Data (Attrition Bias)	Selective Reporting (Reporting Bias)	Other Bias Overall
Wang et al.,	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	High	Some Concern
Sonjelle Shilton et al.,	High	Low	Low	Low	High	High	Some Concern
Drobnik et al.,	Low	Low	Low	Some concern	Some concern	Some concern	Low Risk of Bias
Wenqian Xu et al.,	High	Low	Low	High	Some concern	Some concern	Low Risk of Bias
Candfield et al.,	High	Low	Low	Low	High	High	Low Risk of Bias
Walker et al.	Low	Low	High	High	Some concern	High	Low Risk of Bias
Di Ciaccio et al.,	Low	Low	Low	Some concern	Low	High	Low Risk of Bias

Interpretation	
Low Risk of Bias	
Some Concern	
High Risk of Bias	

The Risk of Bias 2 (ROB 2) tool is a methodological instrument created by the Cochrane Collaboration to evaluate the potential for bias in randomized controlled trials (RCTs). It assesses the internal validity of a research by examining several areas where bias might potentially arise. The instrument evaluates the randomization method, allocation concealment, blinding of participants and staff, blinding of outcome assessment, inadequate outcome data, selective reporting, and overall bias. Research conducted using proper randomization techniques, such as computer-generated random sequences or random number tables, has a reduced likelihood of bias. There is less chance of bias in studies that use strong allocation concealment techniques, such as centralized randomization or opaque, sealed envelopes that are numbered consecutively. Personnel and participants are blinded to the interventions in order to reduce the possibility of bias. Blinding of outcome assessors reduces the risk of biased outcome assessment. Incomplete outcome data is assessed to determine if there are missing data and how they were handled. Selective reporting ensures that all pre-specified outcomes are reported to avoid selective reporting bias. Overall, the study's bias is rated as minimal, moderate concern, or strong based on the evaluations of these areas.

Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS)

The Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) is a quality assessment tool that uses a star system to score studies on a scale of 0–9. The scale has eight items across three domains, and each item is graded one point, except for comparability, which can score up to two points. If a study gets a score between 7 and 9, it's of good quality. If it gets a score between 4 and 6, it's at high risk, and if it gets a score of 0 [63].

The total score is based on the points awarded for each item, as follows:

- Selection: 4 points
 - Comparability: 2 points
 - Outcomes: 3 points
- The scores are interpreted as follows:
- 7–9: High quality
 - 4–6: High risk
 - 0–3: Very high risk of bias

Table 4: Quality assessment (Newcastle-Ottawa Scale)

Study	Selection	Comparability	Outcome	Total score
[13]	4	0	3	7
[14]	4	0	3	7
[15]	4	0	3	7
[16]	4	0	3	7
[17]	4	0	3	7
[18]	4	0	3	7
[19]	4	0	3	7
[10]	4	1	3	8
[20]	4	1	3	8

[21]	4	1	3	8
[22]	4	0	3	7
[23]	4	0	3	7
[24]	4	0	3	7
[25]	4	0	3	7
[27]	4	0	3	7
[28]	4	0	3	7
[29]	4	0	3	7
[30]	4	0	3	7
[31]	4	0	3	7
[32]	4	0	3	7
[33]	4	0	3	7
[34]	4	0	3	7
[35]	4	0	3	7
[36]	4	0	3	7
[37]	4	0	3	7
[39]	4	0	3	7
[40]	4	0	3	7
[41]	4	0	3	7
[13]	4	0	3	7
[14]	4	0	3	7
[15]	4	0	3	7
[16]	4	0	3	7
[17]	4	0	3	7
[18]	4	0	3	7

Discussion

The current study looks at how useful, possible, and acceptable oral HCV fast antibody tests are as self-tests. The results can help with the development of HCV self-testing programs and study in areas where people are highly likely to get or pass on the virus. Most of the studies concluded that, the HCV self-testing review shows that important parts of the test are possible. For example, people can provide their own samples for testing, oral fluid-based tests are acceptable and workable, and quick HCV tests can be done at the point of care in community settings. An experiment in Egypt discovered that oral fluid HCV self-testing is possible and acceptable for key groups of people to take. In Malaysia, the general population and males who engage in sexual activity with other men (MSM) are very receptive to HCV self-

testing, which involves the use of oral fluids or blood. Similarly, individuals who inject drugs (PWID) in Kenya are also highly receptive to HCV self-testing, but they often commit errors that are associated with withdrawal symptoms. In Guangzhou, China, oral fluid HCV self-testing was found to be simple and accepted among key disadvantaged groups, with 54% of those who took the test properly reading the data. To make the method work better, more application study is needed. Observational studies were done on the usefulness of the HCV self-testing in five countries: China, Egypt, Kenya, Vietnam, and Georgia. The study found that the system was highly acceptable and easy to use. The most common mistake was seen when samples were being collected. Most of the people who took the test did it on their own, but most PWID needed help. In Egypt and Kenya, the percentage of people who said HCV self-testing was easy or very easy ranged from 55% to 66%. It has been found that drug users and men who have sex with other guys are very open to taking the HCV Self-Test. But there isn't much agreement between HCV self-testing and study staff. Self-testing for HIV could make it easier for people on the border between San Diego and Tijuana to get tested. But it has problems, like not having therapy and the chance of mental hurt. Even though the EPIC-HIV1 computer app is easy to use, getting to doctors can be hard. Some of the suggestions are to raise knowledge, make it easier for people to access, focus efforts, and test the directions. Researchers looked at how much HCV self-testing cost to identify and treat in four different settings. They found that it enhanced the numeral of people who were tested, recognized, and rehabilitated, but it cost more than standard of care. The extra cost for each diagnosis was higher than the standard of care. The differences were caused by how common the diagnosis was in each setting. It's possible that HCV self-testing is more cost-effective in places where it's more common. A study in China found that self-testing for HIV has a big effect on the number of men who have sexual relationships with other men (MSM) who get tested for HIV. It is cheaper than traditional healthcare and gives people the chance to make their own decisions, learn, and keep their results private and secret. However, high-risk groups in low-resource situations often don't get tested for HIV because of shame, bias, and worries about privacy. In Canada, the INSTI HIV-1/2 Antibody Self-Test is the first screening tool, but test results are often wrong in real life. A study in Metro Manila, Philippines, looked at how useful it would be to have HIV testing that doesn't need help. They found that 9.8% of people there had HIV and that 95% of the tests worked. The HIVST systematic review found that HCV self-testing raised the number of tests done and the number of positive tests compared to routine testing. It's useful for many groups and users because it gives private, secret findings, freedom to make choices, and more education. HCV self-testing is easy to use, doesn't cost much, and is fair, so it can reach more people and maybe make things fairer in a wider range of settings.[64]. The HCV Rapid Antibody Test was evaluated for its performance on oral fluid specimens by 95 participants. Participants self-collected their specimens and interpreted their results, with a researcher interpreting the test simultaneously. The test showed a sensitivity and specificity of 88.4% and 100% when patients interpreted the results, and 97.7% and 98% when trained staff interpreted the results. The κ statistic was 0.89, indicating good performance in self-testing oral fluid specimens. A study looked at the difference in cost between HCV self-testing and facility-based testing services in China, Georgia, Vietnam, and Kenya. The study revealed that HCV self-testing enhanced the number of individuals tested, diagnosed, and cured, albeit at a higher cost. It is more cost-effective to use HCV self-testing in areas where it is common. Hepatitis C self-testing is an innovative approach to increase access to testing for those not reached by current methods. However, it has potential errors and psychosocial harm. Future research should focus on acceptability and feasibility of service delivery models. Rapid HCV self-testing kits could help inject drug users know their status and seek treatment.

Conclusion

The study establishes the feasibility and high acceptability of oral fluid HCV self-testing, which has the potential to eliminate obstacles to facility-based HCV testing. As a result, it becomes a viable option for extending HCV testing. Self-testing for HIV is easier than getting tested by a provider, but it may not be widely used because it is more expensive, doesn't offer face-to-face counseling, and isn't very good at connecting people to care. There are two steps to checking for HIV. First, a positive serology test is used to prove that the person has HIV. To help people get care, HCV self-testing

needs special tactics and messages. Still, HCV self-testing might be able to help get people tested who haven't been reached yet, like teens, college students, and people from underrepresented groups who might not want to use current testing services or don't have easy access to healthcare facilities. The study emphasizes the necessity of enhancing instructions, enhancing test kits, and offering support resources to enhance the user-friendliness of HCV self-testing. The expense associated with HCV self-testing may hinder its adoption, indicating the need for subsidized or partially subsidized alternatives. This study contributes significantly to the existing body of information on self-care interventions, providing valuable data for self-care programs and research endeavors. HCV self-testing has the potential to decrease undetected infections and enhance the availability of healthcare treatments. The results indicate that future HIV/AIDS testing self-testing in other countries and settings should prioritize simplifying self-testing and reducing the likelihood of errors. We can simplify test processes, improve gadgets, clarify instructions, and provide support tools like educational films, online and in-person help, phone hotlines, social media resources, and mobile apps to achieve this. We properly used these tools during the HIV self-testing roll-out.

Data Availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and its supplementary materials. See Appendix-1.

References

- [1] Mohd Hanafiah, K., Groeger, J., Flaxman, A. D., & Wiersma, S. T. (2013). Global epidemiology of hepatitis C virus infection: new estimates of age-specific antibody to HCV seroprevalence. *Hepatology*, 57(4), 1333-1342. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hep.26141>
- [2] Datta, S., Horwood, J., Hickman, M., & Sharp, D. (2014). Case-finding for hepatitis C in primary care: a mixed-methods service evaluation. *The British Journal of General Practice*, 64(618), e67-e74. <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp14X677112>
- [3] Barocas, J. A., Brennan, M. B., Hull, S. J., Stokes, S., Fangman, J. J., & Westergaard, R. P. (2014). Barriers and facilitators of hepatitis C screening among people who inject drugs: a multi-city, mixed-methods study. *Harm Reduction Journal*, 11(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1477-7517-11-1>
- [4] Manns, M. P., Buti, M., Gane, E., et al. (2017). Hepatitis C virus infection. *Nature Reviews Disease Primers*, 3(1), 17006. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrdp.2017.6>
- [5] Njuguna, H. N., Hiebert, L., Harris, A., Morgan, R. L., Gupta, N., & Ward, J. W. (2023). An assessment of national strategic action plans for viral hepatitis elimination, 2016-2021. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 228(Supplement_1), S148-S153. <https://doi.org/10.1093/infdis/jiad346>
- [6] Waked, I., Esmat, G., Elsharkawy, A., et al. (2020). Screening and treatment program to eliminate hepatitis C in Egypt. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 382(12), 1166-1174.
- [7] Oru, E., Trickey, A., Shirali, R., Kanters, S., & Easterbrook, P. (2021). Decentralisation, integration, and task-shifting in hepatitis C virus infection testing and treatment: a global systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Global Health*, 9(4), e431-e445. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(20\)30505-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30505-2)
- [8] Figueroa, C., Johnson, C., Ford, N., et al. (2018). Reliability of HIV rapid diagnostic tests for self-testing compared with testing by health-care workers: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet HIV*, 5(6), e277-e290. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-3018\(18\)30044-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-3018(18)30044-4)
- [9] Guise, A., Witzel, T. C., Mandal, S., et al. (2018). A qualitative assessment of the acceptability of hepatitis C remote self-testing and self-sampling amongst people who use drugs in London, UK. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 18(1), 281. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-018-3185-7>
- [10] Kimble, M. M., Stafylis, C., Treut, P., Saab, S., & Klausner, J. D. (2019). Clinical evaluation of a hepatitis C antibody rapid immunoassay on self-collected oral fluid specimens. *Diagnostic Microbiology and Infectious Disease*, 95(2), 149-151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diagmicrobio.2019.05.010>

- [11] Poynard, T., Yuen, M. F., Ratzin, V., & Lai, C. L. (2003). Viral hepatitis C. *The Lancet*, 362(9401), 2095-2100.
- [12] Walker, J. G., Ivanova, E., Jamil, M. S., et al. (2023). Cost-effectiveness of hepatitis C virus self-testing in four settings. *PLOS Global Public Health*, 3(2), e0001667. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0001667>
- [13] Perazzo, H., Castro, R., Villela-Nogueira, C., et al. (2023). Acceptability and usability of oral fluid HCV self-testing for hepatitis C diagnosis: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Viral Hepatitis*, 30(10), 838-847. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jvh.13876>
- [14] Reipold, E. I., Farahat, A., Elbeeh, A., et al. (2021). Usability and acceptability of self-testing for hepatitis C virus infection among the general population in the Nile Delta region of Egypt. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), 1188. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11169-x>
- [15] Chan, H. K., Sem, X., Ivanova Reipold, E., et al. (2024). Usability and acceptability of oral fluid- and blood-based hepatitis C virus self-testing among the general population and men who have sex with men in Malaysia. *PLOS Global Public Health*, 4(1), e0001770. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0001770>
- [16] Ivanova Reipold, E., Fajardo, E., Juma, E., et al. (2022). Usability and acceptability of oral fluid hepatitis C self-testing among people who inject drugs in Coastal Kenya: a cross-sectional pilot study. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 22(1), 738. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-022-07712-9>
- [17] Fajardo, E., Watson, V., Kumwenda, M., et al. (2022). Usability and acceptability of oral-based HCV self-testing among key populations: a mixed-methods evaluation in Tbilisi, Georgia. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 22(1), 510. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-022-07484-2>
- [18] Xu, W., Reipold, E. I., Zhao, P., et al. (2022). HCV self-testing to expand testing: a pilot among men who have sex with men in China. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 903747. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.903747>
- [19] Nguyen, L. T., Nguyen, V. T. T., Le Ai, K. A., et al. (2021). Acceptability and usability of HCV self-testing in high risk populations in Vietnam. *Diagnostics*, 11(2), 377. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics11020377>
- [20] Walker, J. G., Ivanova, E., Jamil, M. S., et al. (2023). Cost-effectiveness of hepatitis C virus self-testing in four settings. *PLOS Global Public Health*, 3(2), e0001667. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0001667>
- [21] Reipold, E. I., Van Nguyen, T. T., Shiha, G., et al. (2021). Hepatitis C virus self-testing: multi-country evidence on usability and acceptability. Recommendations and guidance on hepatitis C virus self-testing. World Health Organization.
- [22] Serumondo, J., Shilton, S., Nshimiyimana, L., et al. (2021). Values and preferences for hepatitis C self-testing among the general population and healthcare workers in Rwanda. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 21(1), 1064. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-021-06773-6>
- [23] World Health Organization. (2021). Recommendations and guidance on hepatitis C virus self-testing: web annex D: values and preferences on hepatitis C virus self-testing.
- [24] Martínez-Pérez, G. Z., Nikitin, D. S., Bessonova, A., Fajardo, E., & Bessonov, S. (2021). Values and preferences for hepatitis C self-testing among people who inject drugs in Kyrgyzstan. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 21(1), 609. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-021-06332-z>
- [25] Majam, M., Fischer, A., Ivanova Reipold, E., Rhagnath, N., Msolomba, V., & Lalla-Edward, S. T. (2021). A lay-user assessment of hepatitis C virus self-testing device usability and interpretation in Johannesburg, South Africa. *Diagnostics*, 11(3), 463. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics11030463>
- [26] Wang, C., Zhao, P., Weideman, A. M., et al. (2023). Expanding hepatitis C virus test uptake using self-testing among men who have sex with men in China: two parallel randomized controlled trials. *BMC Medicine*, 21(1), 279. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-023-02981-w>
- [27] Fonner, V. A., Kautsar, H., Eshun-Wilson, I., et al. (2021). Hepatitis C virus self-testing: systematic review report. Recommendations and guidance on hepatitis C virus self-testing. World Health Organization.

- [28] Balakrishnan, P., Smiline Girija, A., & Shanmugam, S., et al. (2023). The implementation of HIV self-testing in resource-limited settings where the HIV disease burden is high. *International Journal of Public Health*, 68, 1605790.
- [29] Pines, H. A., Eger, W. H., Skaathun, B., et al. (2024). Willingness to use and distribute HIV self-testing kits among people who inject drugs in the San Diego–Tijuana border region. *Harm Reduction Journal*, 21(1), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12954-023-00922-7>
- [30] Peiper, N. C., Shamblen, S., Gilbertson, A., et al. (2022). Acceptability of a HIV self-testing program among people who use illicit drugs. *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 103, 103613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2022.103613>
- [31] Ballard, A. M., Haardöerfer, R., Prood, N., Mbagwu, C., Cooper, H. L. F., & Young, A. M. (2021). Willingness to participate in at-home HIV testing among young adults who use opioids in rural Appalachia. *AIDS and Behavior*, 25(2), 699-708. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-020-03034-6>
- [32] Hlongwa, M., Hlongwana, K., Makhunga, S., et al. (2023). Linkage to HIV care following HIV self-testing among men: systematic review of quantitative and qualitative studies from six countries in sub-Saharan Africa. *AIDS and Behavior*, 27(2), 651-666. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-022-03800-8>
- [33] Mason, J., & Bailey, S. (2023). Rapid HIV self-testing. *Canadian Journal of Health Technologies*, 3.
- [34] Nash, S. G., Maffeo, M., Likatavicius, G., et al. (2021). Acceptability and usability of HIV self-tests in two European countries: findings from surveys of clients at non-governmental organisations in Lithuania and Italy. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 21(1), 844. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-021-06442-8>
- [35] Rosadiño, J. D. T., Pagtakhan, R. G., Briñes, M. T., et al. (2023). Implementation of unassisted and community-based HIV self-testing (HIVST) during the COVID-19 pandemic among men-who-have-sex-with-men (MSM) and transgender women (TGW): a demonstration study in Metro Manila, Philippines. *PLOS One*, 18(2), e0282644.
- [36] Dlamini, N., Gumede, V., Mathenjwa, T., et al. (2020). Acceptability of a tablet-based application to support early HIV testing among men in rural KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa: a mixed method study.
- [37] Kimble, M. M., Stafylis, C., Treut, P., Saab, S., & Klausner, J. D. (2019). Clinical evaluation of a hepatitis C antibody rapid immunoassay on self-collected oral fluid specimens. *Diagnostic Microbiology and Infectious Disease*, 95(2), 149-151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diagmicrobio.2019.05.010>
- [38] Shilton, S., Stvilia, K., Japaridze, M., et al. (2022). Home-based hepatitis C self-testing in people who inject drugs and men who have sex with men in Georgia: a protocol for a randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Open*, 12(4), e056243.
- [39] Bajis, S., Applegate, T. L., Grebely, J., Matthews, G. V., & Dore, G. J. (2020). Novel hepatitis C virus (HCV) diagnosis and treatment delivery systems: facilitating HCV elimination by thinking outside the clinic. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 222(Supplement_9), S758-S772. <https://doi.org/10.1093/infdis/jiaa366>
- [40] Martínez-Pérez, G. Z., Nikitin, D. S., Bessonova, A., Fajardo, E., & Bessonov, S., & Shilton, S. (2021). Values and preferences for hepatitis C self-testing among people who inject drugs in Kyrgyzstan. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 21(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-021-06332-z>
- [41] Applegate, T. L., Fajardo, E., & Sacks, J. A. (2018). Hepatitis C virus diagnosis and the holy grail. *Infectious Disease Clinics*, 32(2), 425-445.
- [42] Duah, E., Mathebula, E. M., & Mashamba-Thompson, T. (2023). Quality assurance for hepatitis C virus point-of-care diagnostics in sub-Saharan Africa. *Diagnostics*, 13(3), 684.
- [43] Drobnik, A., Judd, C., Banach, D., Egger, J., Konty, K., & Rude, E. (2011). Public health implications of rapid hepatitis C screening with an oral swab for community-based organizations serving high-risk populations. *American Journal of Public Health*, 101(11), 2151-2155.
- [44] Xu, W., Reipold, E. I., Zhao, P., et al. (2022). HCV self-testing to expand testing: a pilot among men who have sex with men in China. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 903747.

- [45] Candfield, S., Samuel, M. I., Ritchie, D., McDonald, C., Brady, M., & Taylor, C. (2017). Use and acceptability of salivary hepatitis C virus testing in an English young offender institution. *International Journal of STD & AIDS*, 28(12), 1234-1238.
- [46] Walker, J. G., Easterbrook, P., & Fajardo, E., et al. (2021). Web annex F cost-effectiveness of hepatitis C virus self-testing.
- [47] Reipold, E. I., Trianni, A., Krakower, D., et al. (2017). Values, preferences and current hepatitis B and C testing practices in low- and middle-income countries: results of a survey of end users and implementers. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 17(1), 702. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-017-2769-y>
- [48] Fonner, V. A., Luhmann, N., Siegfried, N., et al. (2023). Use of indirect evidence from HIV self-testing to inform the WHO hepatitis C self-testing recommendation. *BMJ Global Health*, 8(4), e011633. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2023-011633>
- [49] Di Ciaccio, M., Villes, V., Perfect, C., et al. (2023). Need for integration of hepatitis C (HCV) services in community-based settings for people who inject drugs: results from a global values and preferences survey. *Harm Reduction Journal*, 20(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12954-023-00743-8>
- [50] Shahid, I., Alzahrani, A. R., Al-Ghamdi, S. S., Alanazi, I. M., Rehman, S., & Hassan, S. (2021). Hepatitis C diagnosis: simplified solutions, predictive barriers, and future promises. *Diagnostics*, 11(7), 1253.
- [51] Peeling, R. W., Boeras, D. I., Marinucci, F., & Easterbrook, P. (2017). The future of viral hepatitis testing: innovations in testing technologies and approaches. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 17(1), 699. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-017-2775-0>
- [52] Shilton, S., Sem, X., Chan, H. K., et al. (2022). A quasi-randomised controlled trial of online distribution of home-based hepatitis C self-testing for key populations in Malaysia: a study protocol. *Trials*, 23(1), 304. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-022-06230-y>
- [53] Thornton, L., Barry, J., Long, J., Allwright, S., Bradley, F., & Parry, J. V. (2000). Comparison between self-reported hepatitis B, hepatitis C, and HIV antibody status and oral fluid assay results in Irish prisoners. *Communicable Disease and Public Health*, 3(4), 253-255.
- [54] Peeling, R. W., Boeras, D. I., Marinucci, F., & Easterbrook, P. (2017). The future of viral hepatitis testing: innovations in testing technologies and approaches. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 17(1), 699. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-017-2775-0>
- [55] Tonen-Wolyec, S., Djang'eing'a, R. M., Batina-Agasa, S., et al. (2021). Self-testing for HIV, HBV, and HCV using finger-stick whole-blood multiplex immunochromatographic rapid test: a pilot feasibility study in sub-Saharan Africa. *PLOS One*, 16(3), e0249701.
- [56] Ivanova Reipold, E., Van Nguyen, T. T., Shiha, G., et al. (2021). Recommendations and guidance on hepatitis C virus self-testing: web annex E: hepatitis C virus self-testing: multi-country evidence on usability and acceptability. World Health Organization.
- [57] Kersh, E. N., Shukla, M., Raphael, B. H., Habel, M., & Park, I. (2021). At-home specimen self-collection and self-testing for sexually transmitted infection screening demand accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic: a review of laboratory implementation issues. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, 59(8), e02646-20. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jcm.02646-20>
- [58] Lu, T., Li, H., Mao, X., et al. (2020). HIV self-testing to promote serostatus disclosure among men who have sex with men in China: protocol for a stepped wedge randomized controlled trial. *JMIR Research Protocols*, 9(8), e17788.
- [59] Mehmood, A., Nawab, S., Jin, Y., Hassan, H., Kaushik, A. C., & Wei, D.-Q. (2023). Ranking breast cancer drugs and biomarkers identification using machine learning and pharmacogenomics. *ACS Pharmacology & Translational Science*, 6(5), 399-409. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsptsci.2c00212>
- [60] Fan, S., Liu, Z., Luo, Z., et al. (2020). Effect of availability of HIV self-testing on HIV testing frequency among men who have sex with men attending university in China (UniTest): protocol of a stepped-wedge randomized controlled trial. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 20(1), 149. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-020-4807-4>

- [61] Banerjee, P., Madhwapathi, V., Thorley, N., & Radcliffe, K. (2020). A service evaluation comparing home-based testing to clinic-based testing for HIV, syphilis and hepatitis B in Birmingham and Solihull. *International Journal of STD & AIDS*, 31(7), 613-618. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956462419900461>
- [62] Khan, M. N. M., Sarwar, G., Irfan, S. D., Gourab, G., Rana, A. K. M. M., & Khan, S. I. (2022). Understanding the barriers of HIV testing services for men who have sex with men and transgender women in Bangladesh: a qualitative study. *Community Health Equity Research & Policy*, 42(4), 309-323. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0272684X21995672>
- [63] Moskalewicz, A., & Oremus, M. (2020). No clear choice between Newcastle-Ottawa Scale and Appraisal Tool for Cross-Sectional Studies to assess methodological quality in cross-sectional studies of health-related quality of life and breast cancer. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 120, 94-103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2019.12.013>
- [64] Guyatt, G. H., Oxman, A. D., Kunz, R., et al. (2011). GRADE guidelines: 8. Rating the quality of evidence--indirectness. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 64(12), 1303-1310. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2011.04.014>

APPENDIX -1

	Signalling questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Domain 1: Risk of bias arising from the randomization process	1.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	NI	Y	Y	NI	NI	NI	Y
	1.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until participants were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	NI	Y	Y	NI	NI	NI	Y
	1.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Risk-of-bias judgement	High	Low	Low	High	High	High	Low
Domain 2: Risk of bias due to deviations from the intended interventions (effect of assignment to intervention)	2.1.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	2.1.2. Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	2.1.3 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Risk-of-bias judgement	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
	2.2.1. Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	2.2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	NI	NI	Y	Y	N	N
	2.2.3. Were important non-protocol interventions balanced across intervention groups?	Y	NI	NI	NI	NI	Y	Y

	2.2.4 Were there failures in implementing the intervention that could have affected the outcome?	PN	PN	PY	PY	PY	PN	PN
	2.2.5. Was there non-adherence to the assigned intervention regimen that could have affected participants' outcomes?	PN	PY	PY	PY	PY	PN	PY
	2.2.6.: Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of adhering to the intervention?	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Risk-of-bias judgement	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	High
Domain 3: Missing outcome data	3.1 Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants randomized?	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	3.2 Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing outcome data?	PN	NI	NI	PN	PN	PN	Y
	3.3 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	3.4 Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Risk-of-bias judgement	Low	low	concern	High	High	Low	High
Domain 4: Risk of bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	PN	NI	Y	Y	PY	PN	PY
	4.3 Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	4.4 Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	PN	PN	PN	PN	PN	PN	PN
	4.5 Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	PN	PN	PN	PN	PN	PN	PN

	Risk-of-bias judgement	High	low	concern	concern	concern	High	concern
Domain 5: Risk of bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	5.2. ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	N	PN	PN	N	N	N
	Risk-of-bias judgement	High	High	concern	concern	High	High	High

Mon Yee Htet Paing
Health Science Centre,
Xi'an Jiao Tong University
76 ,Yanta West Road, Xi'an City,Shannxi Province, 710061

Ye Win Naing
Health Science Centre,
Xi'an Jiao Tong University
76 ,Yanta West Road, Xi'an City,Shannxi Province, 710061

Khin Yadana Aung
Health Science Centre,
Xi'an Jiao Tong University
76 ,Yanta West Road, Xi'an City,Shannxi Province, 710061

